
Rainfall Variability In Pune Division (1901 to 2023)

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Abstract:

With the help of simple trend attempt has been made to study the variation of rainfall in Pune division. The trends in the monthly, seasonal, annual and decadal average rainfall of Pune division have been studied from 1901 to 2023. The study discusses development of a gridded rainfall data over Pune division high spatial $0.25^{\circ} \times 0.25$ resolution; it's included 94 grid points. The purpose of the present study is to examine rainfall trend over an extensive time interval and a wide area. Statistical analysis of the database highlights increase and decrease rainfall trend over the last 123 years.

Keywords: Rainfall, Gridded data, Trend, Division, Distribution.

Introduction:

Precipitation trend analyses, on different spatial and temporal scales, has been of great concern during the past century because of the attention given to global climate change from the scientific community: they indicate a small positive global trend, even though large areas are instead characterized by negative trends (IPCC, 1996). Rainfall uncertainty is one among the slices of climate variation which has a vital role in many aspects like ecological, economical and aesthetical diversity of the country. In India many studies have been done to investigate the significance of rainfall events with a special concern of monsoonal change and global warming (Balchandran, 2006). In this paper attempt has been made to study an annual variability of rainfall in Pune division over the period 1901 to 2023. The availability of rainfall data is in the form of station wise and gridded. The annual rainfall trend was increases up to 129.95 mm in last 123 years. The average annual rainfall in the study area

was 1467.9 mm. For the purpose of spatial distribution of rainfall the researcher has been used grids $0.25^{\circ} \times 0.25^{\circ}$ during the same period. In the process of annual trend of rainfall, an atmospheric change plays dominant role or its impact on changing the nature of rainfall, (Ramchandran A. 2014). The second cause behind the spatial nature of rainfall in study region is topographic variation.

Study Area:

The Pune division is located in southwestern part of Maharashtra state. It lies between $15^{\circ}, 45' N$ to $19^{\circ}, 0' N$ latitude and $73^{\circ}, 32' E$ to $76^{\circ}, 15' E$ longitude. The area under study comprises of five districts namely Pune, Sangli, Satara, Solhapur, and Kolhapur (Pune Division). The study region occupies a total geographical area of 57275 sq km and habitating 23,449,051 populations as per 2011 census. Physiographical this region can be divided in to three parts namely hilly, plateau and lowlands. In this region temperature is varies

in the internal different parts, the maximum average temperature of the study area is 31.82° C and minimum 20.33° C. An average annual rainfall in the Pune division is 1467.9 mm. There are major two river basins, which are Krishna and Bhima. Most part of the Pune Division has covered by medium black soil.

Fig. No. 1

Data Base and Methodology:

Indian Metrological Department (IMD), Pune has provided monthly station wise rainfall data over Pune Division from 1901 to 2023. The Pune division yearly rainfall and temperature data had taken from the website (www.indiawaterportal.in), from 1901 to 20023. The Pune Division 0.25° by 0.25° gridded rainfall data had obtained from Global Weather Data website from 1979 to 2023. Gridded data are also preferred for the model validations, as the model outputs are generated at fixed spatial grid points. However, depending on the application, requirement of spatial and temporal resolution of the gridded data can be different. (Pai, D. 2014). The rainfall trend calculated with the help of MS- Excel

Windows office 2023. The analyzed data is annual, decadal monthly and season wise for the considering period. The mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation has been calculated. Here the variability of the annual rainfall has been calculated by using the formula: Coefficient of Variation = Standard Deviation / Mean *100. The spatial distribution of rainfall shows with the help of using Arc Map GIS software.

Objectives:

1. To analyze rainfall trend in the Pune Division.
2. To study the changes in spatio-temporal rainfall in study region.

Annual Rainfall Trend in Pune Division:

A temporal trend describes the long smooth movement of the variable lasting over a span of observations, ignoring the short term fluctuation. The analysis of trend is primarily estimation of the magnitude of trend along with the statistical significance of the value (p -value). Identification of long-term trends in climate change provide information for decision-makers and resource managers that allow them to better anticipate and plan for the potential impacts of climate variability and change (Singh Vivekanand, 2017).

The mean annual rainfall over the Pune division is 1467.90 mm during the period of 123 years (1901-2023). The coefficient of variation of annual rainfall is relatively low (17.8 %). The mean annual rainfall over Pune Division from 1901 to 2023 is showing an in decreasing trend by 129.95 mm (fig.1.a). The increasing trend was notated by 1.15 mm per year. The mean lowest and highest rainfalls were reported 1492.08 mm, which is lowest in 1917 and the highest in 1994 (2029.90 mm).

Table No.1: Monthly Rainfall Trend in Pune Division (1901 to 2023)

Year	Average	S. D.	C.V.	In %
January	0.40	1.60	353.10	0.03
February	1.10	2.60	232.10	0.08
March	2.60	3.40	128.40	0.18
April	15.00	13.00	86.70	1.02
May	44.30	40.10	90.50	3.02
June	333.20	117.80	35.40	22.70
July	452.60	148.30	32.80	30.84
August	290.00	112.70	38.90	19.76
September	188.00	89.30	47.50	12.81
October	98.90	63.90	64.60	6.74
November	35.30	39.10	110.70	2.40
December	6.40	11.60	181.80	0.43
Winter Rainfall	7.90	11.80	149.10	0.54
Summer Rainfall	61.90	42.40	68.40	4.22
SW Monsoon	1263.90	244.50	19.30	86.10
Post Monsoon	134.20	75.10	56	9.14
Annual	1467.90	2610	17.80	100.00

Source: Computed by Researcher, 2025

The decadal trend in mean rainfall over Pune division is observed that increases which is account for 12.51 mm/decade. The decadal mean rainfall recorded was the highest (1628.10 mm) in 1951-60 followed by (1529.5 mm) in 1961-70 and (1524 mm) in 1931-40. The lowest mean rainfall is

recorded in 2011-20 decade and that was 1171 mm followed by 1296.8 in 1921-30 (fig.1.b). The annual decadal rainfall trend increases till 1930 to 1950 continuous increases and there was significant decreases.

Fig. 2 Annual Rainfall Trend in Pune Division (1901 to 2023)

Fig. 3 Decadal Rainfall Trend in Pune Division (1901 to 2023)

Seasonal Rainfall Trend in Pune Division:

A trend is a significant change over time exhibited by a random variable, detectable by statistical parametric and non-parametric procedures (Longobardi A. and Villani P. 2009). The SW Monsoon rainfall over the Pune division is 1263.9 mm during the period of 123 years (1901-2023). The table no. 1.0 shows that the coefficient of variation of SW Monsoon rainfall is 19.30 per cent. The CV is in the month of June reporting 35.40 per cent, July (32.80 %), and

August (38.90 %) are relatively low variation as compare to the September (47.50 %). The SW Monsoon rainfall over Pune Division from 1901 to 2023 presented an increasing trend of 129.95 mm (fig.2.a.). The increasing was at the rate of 0.72 mm per year. The SW Monsoon was the lowest (1492.08 mm) in 1917 and the highest (426.72 mm) in 1918. The Post Monsoon rainfall over the Pune division is 134.2 mm during considering period of 123 years.

Fig. 4 Seasonal Rainfall Trend in Pune Division (1901 to 2023) a. SW monsoon, b. Post Monsoon, c. Summer, d. Winter

The Table No. 1.0 shows that coefficient variation of Post Monsoon rainfall is 56.00 per cent. The Post Monsoon rainfall over Pune Division from 1901 to 2023 is presented an increasing trend by 52.19 mm (fig.2.b). The increase in post

monsoon rainfall is an estimated and that rate of increasing is 0.46 mm per year. The Post Monsoon was the lowest reported in year 1907 (14.23 mm) and the highest 375.58 mm in 2010. The summer rainfall over the Pune division is 61.9 mm during the

period 1901-2023. The table no.1 shows that coefficient of variation of summer rainfall is 68.40 per cent. The summer rainfall decreases insignificant level which is 3.16 mm is observed from 1901 to 2023 (fig.2.c). The decreasing in rainfall is at the rate of 0.032 mm per year. The summer rainfall is reported lowest, which is 6.04 mm in 2023 and the highest in 1961 (188.51 mm).

The winter rainfall over the Pune division is 7.9 mm. during the period of 123 years (1901-2023).The table 1 shows that coefficient of variation of winter rainfall is (149.1 %). The winter rainfall increases insignificant level, which is 0.34 mm, is observed in considering period (fig.2.d). The increasing in rainfall is noted at the rate of 0.003 mm per year. The winter rainfall was the lowest in 1953 (0.0164mm) and the highest in 1962 (57.88 mm). The rainfall maybe attributed to a declining trend in the frequency of depressions, cyclonic storms and systems during the months June to September (Singh P., and Sharma, S., 2017).

Conclusion:

The annual rainfall trend of Pune division from 1901 to 2023 was increases 129.95 mm. he rainfall trend was increases SW monsoon (81.60 mm), post monsoon (52.19 mm) and winter rainfall increases (0.64 mm) insignificant level. The summer rainfall trend was decreases in 3.61 mm during the 123 years in the Pune division. Precipitation conditions over Pune division during the considering years show that trend of increases annual rainfall. The south-west, post and winter rainfall trend increases while the summer rainfall trend is decreases insignificant.

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